

Sample Name: PVC Vir Flu 5-10 µm

Material: Polyvinyl Chloride

Size: 5-10 µm

Supplier: SigmaAldrich Merck, no. 346764, powder, Aimplas, TNO

Density: 1,4 (g/cm³)*

Production Partner: TNO

Storage Conditions: Refrigerated and dark

*The density may vary due to the presence of Fluorescein

Summary

Physical Characteristics

- Median diameter (D_{50_v}) = 6,06 µm
- Particles have an irregular morphology
- 3.1×10^{13} particles per gram
- 11689 cm²/g surface area

Chemical Characteristics

- Fluorescent moiety is Fluorescein
- C=O peak (1733 cm⁻¹) indicating the presence of Fluorescein

Description of terms

- D[4,3]:Volume mean (µm)
- D[3,2]:Surface area mean (µm)
- D[2,1]: Spherical particle mean (µm)
- D[1,0]: Number length mean (µm)
- D_{50_v} : Median diameter (volume basis, µm)
- D_{50_N} : Median diameter (number basis, µm)
- N_w : Number of particles per gram plastic (#/g)
- A_w : Surface area of particles per gram plastic (cm²/g)

Particle Size Distribution (using *Static Light Scattering (SLS)* provided by TNO)

D[4,3]	D[3,2]	D[2,1]	D[1,0]	D50 _N	D50 _V	N _w	A _w
10,47	3,72	1,19	0,54	0,34	6,06	3.1×10^{13}	11689

Chemical Bonding (Using μ -FTIR provided by TNO)

